

Communicating Astronomy with the Public Conference 2022 – At a glance

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The world's largest conference on astronomy communication, Communicating Astronomy with the Public Conference, was held from 12-16 September 2022. This edition was held in-person at Macquarie University in Sydney, Australia and online – the conference series's first hybrid event. It was co-organised by the International Astronomical Union (IAU) Commission C2 – Communicating Astronomy with the Public (CAP) and the IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach.

The conference featured 5 keynote speakers, 30 invited talks, 92 parallel talks, two discussion panels, 13 workshops, and

48 posters, in addition to our online programme, which featured meet-ups, virtual poster sessions, a lightning poster session, and more. The participants represented 44 different countries. Of the 111 in-person and 130 online participants were professionals from science communication, informal education, planetariums and science centres, as well as professional and amateur astronomers, journalists and artists.

Throughout the five-day conference, our diverse group of both online and in-person participants gathered together to address our central theme: "Communicating

Astronomy for a Better World." They addressed a wide variety of topics, from astronomy communication in planetariums to the role of astronomy in bridging cultures to current challenges in astronomy communication. We look forward to the exciting conversations you all will engage in during the next CAP Conference online and at Cité de l'espace in Toulouse, France, in June 2024. Nous espérons vous y voir [We hope to see you there]! For more information, see the CAP Conferences website: <https://capconferences.org/>

